

UDC: 159.982.2

orcid.org/0000-0003-2574-9985

S.B. Kuzikova
State A.S. Makarenko Pedagogical
University, Sumy

THEORETICAL APPLICABLE MODELING OF PSYCHOCORRECTION AND PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT

In the article the possibilities of purposeful formation of the subject of self-development in the context of providing psychological assistance have been considered. The author's concept of formation of the subject of self-development in the practice of psychological correction has been presented. The content of psychological support of self-development of the person as a holistic system of training for means of self-development has been determined.

Keywords: self-development, self-consciousness, self-regulation, self-correction, anticipation, subject of self-development, psychological resources of personal self-development, factors and regularities of formation of the subject of self-development.

С.Б. Кузікова

ТЕОРЕТИКО-ПРИКЛАДНЕ МОДЕЛЮВАННЯ ПСИХОКОРЕКЦІЇ ТА РОЗВИТКУ ОСОБИСТОСТІ

В статті розглянуто можливості цілеспрямованого формування суб'єкта саморозвитку в контексті надання психологічної допомоги. Подана авторська концепція формування суб'єкта саморозвитку в практиці психологічної корекції. Визначено зміст психологічного супроводу саморозвитку особистості як цілісної системи навчання засобом саморозвитку.

Ключові слова: саморозвиток, самосвідомість, саморегуляція, самокорекція, антиципація, суб'єкт саморозвитку, психологічні ресурси особистісного саморозвитку, чинники та закономірності становлення суб'єкта саморозвитку.

С.Б. Кузікова

ТЕОРЕТИКО-ПРИКЛАДНОЕ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ ПСИХОКОРРЕКЦИИ И РАЗВИТИЯ ЛИЧНОСТИ

В статье рассмотрены возможности целенаправленного формирования субъекта саморазвития в контексте оказания психологической помощи. Представлена авторская концепция формирования субъекта саморазвития в практике психологической коррекции. Определено содержание психологического сопровождения саморазвития личности как целостной системы обучения средствам саморазвития.

Ключевые слова: саморазвитие, самосознание, саморегуляция, самокоррекция, антиципация, субъект саморазвития, психологические ресурсы личностного саморазвития, факторы и закономерности становления субъекта саморазвития.

Relevance of research and problem statement. The most important task of practical psychology is to assist a person in self-actualization and self-realization of his inner potential, in achieving the harmony of his inner world, improving subjective well-being and strengthening psychological health. It is significant that from the point of view of many modern psychologist-practitioners of different psychotherapeutic areas (humanistic, existential, transpersonal, etc.) self-development of the individual is considered as a necessary condition for his optimal functioning, and stopping self-development, regardless of the cause, causes various personal and psychological disorders (A. Adler, R. Assagioli, J. Bugental, A. Maslow, V. Frankl, K. Horney, etc.). In today's psychological science, the idea is that the process of self-development – as an essential form of human existence – begins with life and unfolds within it (M.Y. Boryshevsky, V.V. Klimenko, G.S. Kostyuk, S. D. Maksimenko, V.I. Slobodchikov, V.A. Tatenko and others). However, actualized and guided self-development is realized only when consciously sets goals for self-knowledge, self-improvement, self-realization, defines the prospects of what it achieves, that is, realizes, objectivises and transforms its own personality characteristics and ways of interaction with the world (K.O. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya, L.I. Antsiferova, S.L. Rubinstein, T.M. Titarenko and others).

From here it is relevant to clarify the possibilities of psychological and pedagogical influence on the person in order to increase its need for positive self-modification in the direction of strengthening subjectivity and the formation of ability to manage self-development. **The purpose of the article** is the presentation of the author's concept of the formation of the subject of self-development in the practice of psychological correction.

Presenting main material. The analysis of the world experience of educational influence on the formation of the individual allowed to find out the possibility of forming the subject of self-development by creating certain conditions and organizing targeted effects on the psychological reality of man, starting with the youngest age. Such impacts can be provided by psychological correction, which promotes the full functioning and development of the individual through the solution of its specific psychological problems, due to the impact on individual psychological structures of a person, fulfilling the task of not only changes but also the training, formation, development of those or other aspects of psychological person's reality.

Comprehensive analysis of the problem of psychocorrection that we have carried out in the historical, cultural, linguistic, scientific and applied aspects, allowed

us to determine in the proper sense of the problem of psychological correction and to develop the author's approach "Age psychocorrection" [1; 3]. Decisive in our approach is the provision that the efficiency and effectiveness of the correction process are determined by the measure of the subject's activity of the person. According to our principled position, it is impossible to make personal correction from the outside. A psychologist, using psycho-correction methods and tactics of his behavior, can only create conditions for the emergence of bright, emotionally colored experiences.

And only these individually unique experiences of a particular person create the possibility of a new vision of her old problems, a new look at the life situation, on themselves, their loved ones and their relationship with them, in their activities. As a rule, most of people do not differentiate and do not describe their own experiences, and their emotional state is felt (and described) in general, for example: "I am bad". Conceptualization and generalization of the experience make it amorphous and implicitly combined with the person as a whole. The aggravation of the same experiences in correctional work contributes to the emergence of such processes: awareness of the phenomena behind them (insight), the response of internal stress (catharsis) and the withdrawal from the psychological reality of the person traumatic circumstances, relationships, individual qualities, emotional states (objectification), and then Separating (distancing) them from the integral self-personality, the further possibility of working on them. Personal knowledge cannot be transmitted from one person to another, from the psychologist to the client, it can only be "produced", taken from one's own experience. There can be no standard of personal knowledge –each one has its own, the other, and not more or less correct, better or worse. Therefore, the main task of a practical psychologist, who carries out psychocorrection, is the development of the skills of personal reflection and self-regulation of clients, the formation of responsibility for their condition and behavior, and, finally, conversion of correction into self-correction. It is about the formation of the subject of his own life and his own development.

The "mechanical" (from the outside, without internal work) solution of psychological problems of man is impossible for such reasons. Individual does not just exist "here and now", but also constantly decides what will be its existence, which it will become at the next moment (V. Frankl). Everyone has the potential for personal development. But for their implementation, it must, firstly, be internally free (autonomous, intentional), and secondly, to see the prospect of its development, to realize the purpose of self-transformation [2, p. 167]. According to K. Obukhovsky, the present is only a point of transition from the future to the past. In order to fully participate in life, it is necessary to adequately anticipate (internal warning, tune in, get used) coming up events. The mechanism of anticipation, researchers consider the basis of self-regulation

and self-development personality (M.Y. Boryshevsky, E.K. Kester, B.F. Lomov, O. Sergienko and others).

The condition associated with the violation of the coherence and consistency of the past, present, future, and the absence of the dominant of the latter, is defined as a neurosis of anticipation (O.M. Arestov, V.D. Mendelevich). A man fixed on his problems, his own experiences, especially psychogenic, lives not even in the present, but in the past, and is guided by this past [5]. Losing the ability to see oneself in the future, she at the same time ceases to be the subject of her own life and self-development.

Thus, focusing on their problems is fixation in the past. The vision of ways to overcome these problems, the inner mood to overcome them – is a direction to the future. When solving problems, planning the future, a person lays a trajectory for his development, that is, he becomes the subject of self-development. Therefore, a person (preferably from an early age) needs to be taught methods, techniques of anti-duplication, mastering of life situations and their own emotional states, which will promote her psychological health and progressive personal self-development.

To determine the ways of forming the subject of self-development, from an early age, from our point of view, the theory of E. Deci and R. Ryan is productive. American researchers postulated the existence of three basic needs, which underlie internal motivation, human intentionality. It is a human's needs for self-determination, competence, and close relationships with other significant people [6].

The need for self-determination (in the autonomy) includes the desire to independently control their actions and behavior, to be their initiator. Her feelings and realization are key to the development of the subject of self-development, since in order to maintain and strengthen the subjectivity, self-development and self-development, a person must experience his behavior as self-deterministic. "It is the ability to choose and make elections, feel themselves, not reinforcements, incentives or some other forces and coercion / pressure from the source of their own actions" [6, p. 38].

The need for competence includes the desire of the subject to achieve different external and internal results and be effective. The development of competence leads to the fact that a person can simulate and assess the effects of their actions in advance and for a long time. This allows him to shift from orientation to external assessment and reinforcement of behavior to the development of "internal standards" for assessing oneself, their plans, life situations and other people, which allows developing resistance to self-reinforcement. This is especially important for the design and implementation of plans at long intervals when there is no external reinforcement.

The need for interconnection with other people involves establishing reliable (and satisfying the individual) relationships with other people, relationships based on the sense of belonging and attachment, which is absolutely necessary condition for the successful formation and functioning of a sense of autonomy at an early age and is manifested in the need for feedback from a meaningful environment in the later.

In the theory of E. Deci and R. Ryan different events are analyzed in terms of their influence on the perception of personality through the locus of causality and competence. According to E. Deci and R. Ryan, the most important task faced by parents and educators is to regulate the child's behavior with external reinforcements in such a way that this regulation is gradually taken by the child himself, becoming his own, and the use of control has not had a negative influence on the child's intrinsic actions in order not to weaken the sense of competence and not to cause the emergence of trained helplessness [6].

We agree with E. Deci and R. Ryan who believe that internal and external motivation do not exist separately from each other, between them transitions are carried out. These transformations are regulated through the process of internalization (the mechanism of self-development – *S.K.*). Researchers distinguish several categories (forms) of external motivation, reflecting different levels of autonomy or self-determination. Ambient behavior of a person is characterized by a lack of intentionality and a sense of personal causality. The following reasons for amotivation are highlighted: a person does not value activity, does not consider it important for himself, does not feel himself competent enough or does not believe that the effort will bring the desired result.

At the lowest level of internalization – the levels of external regulation – the behavior is completely regulated from the outside of the promised rewards or the threat of punishment. This level is characterized by a lack of sense of self-determination behavior. At the next level (introjected regulation), the behavior of the subject is regulated in part by the rules or requirements that prompt him to act so, and not otherwise. The most characteristic features of the presence in the individual introjected regulation is the feeling of guilt and shame. With introjected regulation, the child internally assigns an assessment (approval or condemnation) given to her behavior from the outside (parents). It is now operating under the influence of internal causes, which, however, have a controlling interpersonal nature.

An even more progressive third level of internalization – identified regulation - occurs when the subject experiences a sense of his own choice of this activity, accepting external goals and values that previously regulated its implementation, identifying with them. With the help of the identification process (the mechanism of self-development – *S.K.*), the child adopts regulation as his own.

The fourth level – integrated regulation – involves the generalization and assimilation of all current identities. This is the most autonomous or self-determined form of external motivation. Regulation of activity through integration is similar to intrinsic motivation in that it is also autonomous. However, intrinsic motivation is characterized by an interest in the activity itself, whereas in the case of integrated self-regulation, interest in activity is not dominant.

Intrinsic motivation is inherent in not only the feeling of choice, but also the pleasure and joy of the work being done. Only internal motivation shows a stable positive relationship with achievements (internal sense of success), personal growth, viability and negative – with anxiety, feelings of insults, defeats, disadvantages.

Styles of self-regulation activities have both age dynamics and individual differences. It is also possible to stop at one of the stages of the formation of subjective behavior. But in favorable psychological and pedagogical conditions and activation of all mechanisms of self-development in this way the technology of formation of the subject of self-development is given.

The nursing of a person is expressed in the fact that in the unexpected situations it does not trigger the mechanism of spontaneous activity, but the mechanism of conscious regulation comes into effect. Therefore, the human guidance on behavior in a changing life situations (active or passive life instructions) can be considered as a personal property of a person and an individual-stylistic characteristic of its self-development. In this regard, in the context of the concept of the formation of a subject of self-development, it is important to consider the nature of the emergence and ways to overcome such a phenomenon and personal guidance, as “learned helplessness” (learned helplessness, the term Seligman) – associated with inadequate passivity and Reduction of human intentionality in a problem situation. With a firm perception of his own helplessness (which does not necessarily correspond to reality), a person does not essentially try to check for himself the competence, the ability to cope with the situation, moreover, even the idea of such an opportunity is squeezed out of consciousness.

Formation of the idea of own helplessness can begin from an early age. Fixing, fixing the internal position “I am competent” or “I am helpless” occurs, as a rule, in school years (junior school and younger adolescent age) when forming “I am a concept”. It is at this time that there is a strong tendency to generalize on the principle: if I am helpless in this situation, then I am helpless always and everywhere. The most severe consequences for human development come when the demonstration of helplessness and obedience gets further reinforcements in the form of hyperopic, which allows you to get from a «secondary benefit» situation. The motive for personal development, growth and mastery of competence in this case is replaced by a systematic demonstration of

helplessness, prompting the human environment to treat it as an “eternal child”, solving all problems instead of it.

In many highly developed countries, social support systems for the marginalized population (who are mostly suffering from trained helplessness) are such that they allow a person to live comfortably at the expense of society, without even trying to contribute to its development. This situation has been considered in recent years in the United States, where a similar lifestyle is typical for 7,5-9% of the population as a threat to national security. In Ukraine, in our opinion, the formation of trained helplessness is in most cases due to the peculiarities of the mentality of the Slavic peoples - the desire to care for and control of their children, and also because of the historical factor - the long years regulated and secured on the minimum standard of living of previous generations under the socialist system.

In the process of finding ways to overcome the learned helplessness of M. Seligman, it was assumed that the experience of successfully confronting difficulties and success in solving problems is necessary for full development. These ideas have been developed in A. Beck's psychotherapeutic concept of treating people who are suffering from depressive waiting for unmanaged events. A. Beck believes that a person needs to be involved in obtaining experience, which leads to a revival of the belief in his competence, for example, the therapeutic situation (games, tasks) with increasing complexity, where everyone at the initial stages is guaranteed success.

These ideas are closely linked to the idea of the need for regular correction of not only the goals of the education system, but also the «toolkit» of practical psychologists (M.O. Kholodna). The problem here is that some teachers and psychologists admire the ideas of «separate» development of those or other traits, individual personality traits and individuality. In this case, the fundamental position that the problem of the life of man in the world (S.L. Rubinshtein) is behind all the problems of the correlation of being and consciousness is often disappearing from the field of consideration.

The inner world of personality and its interaction with the outside world are phenomena of a multidimensional nature. From the analysis of the problem of self-development [2] it becomes clear that self-development of a personality is a complex, multidimensional process that has its own dynamics (peaks and downsides), individual orientation, motives, methods, subjective and objective results. We have proposed a conceptual model of the psychological space of self-development of the individual, which reflects the individual peculiarity of organization of personal self-development (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Psychological space of self-development of personality

The concept of formation of the subject of self-development, developed by us, makes it possible to correlate the dimensions of the psychological space of self-development of the individual with the psychological resources of personal self-development determined by us, namely: the need for self-development as its source and determinant; Conditions that ensure its success; Mechanisms as means and conditions for its implementation, as well as with defined criteria for self-development as an informed and self-directed process of personality changes. The criteria for self-development are defined: firstly, actualization of psychological resources of self-development; Secondly, the formation of the attitude towards self-development as to a value – valued orientation to self-development, which appears to be on the outside in cognitive and creative activity, self-enhancement, self-enrichment, and authenticity; And thirdly, the formation of reflexive self-regulation, which appears to be manifest

in the viability of the individual, intelligence of life, internality, etc. Such a possibility of correlation of measurements of the psychological space of self-development of a person with its resources and criteria allows us to analyze holistically (we have developed methodological approaches and means of research) and determine the ways of activation and optimization of self-development of personality as a subject activity [2].

An important point in developing the concept of the formation of the subject of self-development was the elucidation of socio-psychological factors and the laws of the formation of the subject of self-development in ontogenesis, formed by stable causal relationships between external and internal conditions. Their inclusion in the educational process will contribute to the activation of the formation of the individual as a subject of self-development [2].

Table 1

Factors and regularities of becoming a subject of self-development

Socio-psychological factors of self-development of personality	The essence of the laws of the formation of the subject of self-development
1	2
The presence of a number of hobbies, visits to circles, sections, active participation in various events	Interest in the world (the system of relations I - the world) promotes the richness and diversity of life and is an area of actual development that provides the basic level of personal self-development, lays a high potential of self-development and becomes the basis for the formation of the need for constant self-improvement.
The presence of a meaningful person with which «sincere» conversations are possible, discussion of vital affairs, life conflicts, behavior and personality characteristics of the environment, heroes of films, books	Developing the skills of reflection, the experience of continuous analysis of what is happening, and in it contributes to the formation of dialogical of self-consciousness, distancing and objectivizing external circumstances and own experiences, which enhances the subjectivity of self-development
Possibility of discussing with the significant person the plans for the future - close and far	Reflections on the desirable, his analysis, the construction of goals and ways to achieve them contribute to the development of life strategies and tactics, the development of experience anticipating future events

1	2
Possibility of own choice and independent actions as a result of a democratic or even a dominant style of upbringing	The childhood experience of decision-making and responsibility for them provides the formation of internal motivation, self-determination, intensify the intentional modalities "I Want", "I must". The realization of one's own choice becomes a conscious necessity
The presence of conscious moral norms (Above-I), high levels of aspiration, motivation for success (but only through internal personal motives), dissatisfaction with the available	The formation in the child of the needs for self-perfection, ideals and values of spirituality intensifies the intentional modality «I must», defines the perspective of personal growth, activates volitional efforts, makes self-development conscious and self-directed
Having experience of teaching methods of overcoming difficult life situations, working on oneself, skills of relationships with people	Acquiring skills of self-regulation, strengthening the intentional modality of «I Can» increases the psychological culture of personality and provides self-development control
The presence of high cognitive activity, openness to information, tolerance to everything new, unassuming, even some predisposition to adventurism, unpredictable actions. At the same time, the risk is conscious and controlled and is based on trust in oneself	Overcurrent creative activity creates new contexts of human existence (style and quality of life), which promotes its personal expansion, beyond the boundaries of the existing, the formation of non-standard thinking, tolerance to a new, unusual and, ultimately, self-development of value and life strategy
Openness before receiving feedback from the environment, above all from significant individuals. Interest in their views, attitude to events, to other people, to themselves. The perception of feedback as additional information, as a vision of reality in a different angle, and not just as a guide to action	Taking into account multidimensionality of the world extends the psychological space of self-development of the individual, actualizes its resource capabilities, becomes the basis for the formation of dialectical thinking, flexibility in attitudes and behavior while maintaining the sovereignty of the Self, which ensures psychological health and enhances human viability

According to our concept, self-development as a subject activity involves the presence of clearly understood goals of its own transformation, the integral self-concept and the concept of one's life (the image of the world and individual ways of interaction with it), as well as personal guidelines - readiness for self-development, freedom of choice and responsibility for him. Therefore, measurements of the psychological space of self-development determine the technology of personal growth of man. The directions of corrective and developmental work in the context of the concept of the formation of the subject of self-development, we see in the actualization of psychological resources of self-development, activating its mechanisms and taking into account socio-psychological factors and patterns of formation of the subject of self-development.

According to our concept, the process of awareness of the sources of their own negative experiences, their objectification and separation (distancing) from the integral I (I am and my problems) must be continuous. This will give a person a sense of inner freedom and power over circumstances, will allow her to feel the subject of their own lives. At the same time, life will be perceived as a chain of life complications, problem situations that can and must be overcome, and these difficulties themselves – as opportunities for personal growth. To teach this way of interaction with the world is the task of the concept of the formation of the subject of self-development in childhood and adolescence, implemented in the author's approach "Age psycho-correction". The elaboration of the theoretical and methodological aspects of age psycho-correction, as well as the experience of our own work on the provision of psychological care, shows the possibility and, undoubtedly, the necessity of organizing the correction process as a holistic system of training in techniques and techniques of self-correction, self-development (see Table 2) in children and adolescence,

In preschool age, self-regulation is often unconscious, but it helps to regulate the relationship between the child and himself and the world. At junior school age there is a consciousness and conscious self-regulation of psycho-emotional states and behavior. In adolescence and youth there is an awareness, analysis of their inner world and interaction with the surrounding world and on its basis - self-determination, self-regulation and self-development of one's own personality (Table 2).

The model of the formation of the subject of self-development allows at the appropriate moment of study of the problem to move from theoretical models and abstractions to the space of the «life path» of man (S.L. Rubinstein), creating conditions for the solution of her initially situationally predetermined problems, and then for the opportunity to exit into the space of «supersituational activity» (V.A. Petrovsky), the movement to perfection through individual creative acts (A. Adler).

Table 2

Training system for self-development in the model of age psycho-correction

Age	The content of psycho-correction work	Self-development level of personality
	Teaching techniques and technical school:	
preschool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • self-regulation of psycho-emotional states and behavior 	Individually-Regulatory
Junior school	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • awareness (objectification and distancing) • self-regulation 	Individually constructive
Teenage and youthful	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • awareness (objectification, distancing) • self-knowledge and self-examination • self-regulation • self-improvement 	Personally reflexive

Conclusion. Therefore, we are convinced that the basic condition for the viability, effective functioning of a person in a constantly changing world is the ability of constructive react to these changes, to rebuild and, in the end, to constant positive change, to self-develop. Therefore, the problem of age of psycho-correction, according to our concept, is the formation of an active subject of his own life and self-development. The substantive content of the psychological support of the formation of the subject of self-development is given in [3; 4].

REFERENCES

1. Кузікова С.Б. Основи психокорекції: навч. посіб. К.: Академвидав, 2012. 320 с.
2. Кузікова С.Б. Психологічні основи становлення суб'єкта саморозвитку в юнацькому віці. Суми: Вид-во МакДен, 2012. 410с.
3. Кузікова С.Б. Теорія і практика вікової психокорекції. Навч. посібник. Суми: ВТД „Університетська книга", 2014. 384 с.
4. Кузікова С.Б. Техніки вікової психокорекції. Навч. посібник. К.: Главник, 2008. 160 с.
5. Хомуленко Т.Б. Структурно-функціональна характеристика тілесного я в умовах психосоматичної кризи. *Особистість як суб'єкт подолання кризових ситуацій: психологічна теорія і практика* / За ред. С.Д. Максименка, С.Б. Кузікової, В.Л. Зливкова. Суми: Вид-во СумДПУ імені А.С.Макаренка, 2017. С. 123-138.
6. Deci E.L., Ryan R.M. Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behav-

ior. New York : Plenum, 1985.

1. Kuzikova S. B. Osnovy psykhokorektsii: navch. posib. K.: Akademvydav, 2012. – 320 s.
2. Kuzikova S.B. Psykholohichni osnovy stanovlennia subiekta samorozvytku v yunatskomu vitsi. Sumy: Vydavnytstvo «MakDen, 2012. 410 s.
3. Kuzikova S.B. Teoriia i praktyka vikovoi psykhokorektsii. Navch. posibnyk. Sumy: VTD „Univertsytetska knyha“, 2014. 384 s.
4. Kuzikova S.B. Tekhniky vikovoi psykhokorektsii. Navch. posibnyk. K.: Hlavnyk, 2008. 160 s.
5. Khomulenko T.B. Strukturno-funktsionalna kharakterystyka tilesnoho ia v umovakh psykhosomatychnoi kryzy. *Osobystist yak subiekt podolannia kryzovykh sytuatsii: psykholohichna teoriia i praktyka* / Za red. S.D. Maksymenka, S.B. Kuzikovoi, V.L. Zlyvkova. Sumy: Vyd-vo SumDPU imeni A.S. Makarenka, 2017. S. 123-138.
6. Deci E.L., Ryan R.M. Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behavior. New York: Plenum, 1985.

Надійшла до редколегії 14.11.2017 р.